

Insect Pest and Diseases of Roses : Symptoms and Control Measures

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As floriculture industry is a important part of Horticulture. It deals with the culture of flowers and ornamental plants. Indoor Plants and flowers have a great impact in sustainable decoration and environmental development. In modern Age rose is the undisputed flowers. It is essentially a flower of the cool climates. Therefore, the natural blooming season of the rose stretches form November to March in the plains of northern India. Under natural conditions, rose bushes go through tree flushes and full periods in a season. The most dramatic flushes roses appear in peak winter i.e. December (Mariyam *et al.* 2004; BSP, 2014 and Smithar *et al.* 2017).

About thousand varieties of loses have been recommended for cultivation in India. These are trees as : (i) Hybrid Tea (ii) Floribunda (iii) Miniatures, (iv) Ramblers and (v) Creepers. Roses are classified under ten colour groups, these are white, yellow, orange/scarlet, red, deep pink, light pink, lavender/move, apricot colour and blends. Roses export is influenced by economic, potential and social factor hence the value may fluctuate from year.

Insect Pests :

Like other crops of agriculture, roses are also affected by insect-pests and diseases, some of which have been found to be very destructive (Hesman and Eshaur 2004 and Ayton 2008). Major insect-pests, diseases and the measure for their control are summarized here.

White Ants:

White ants or termites are important one and cause severe damage in plants of different varieties of roses. They formed small colonies inside the soil and multiply very rapidly during the rainy season and used to destroy the underground part including the roots of the young as well as old plants. Sometimes1 rose/plants are found apparently healthy in look but they become weak in actual form in winter. The best measure to avoid damage is to apply 5 percent BHC or aldrin in the pits before planting roses. Drenching of rose beds with aldrin also controls the damage of plants in established gardens.

White Grubs:

It is a troublesome pest which are found in underground. Grubs eat the underground portion of roots, bark stem and damage to the extent of death of healthy plants. Soil applications of BHC; lindane and thimet have been found effective for control of white grubs.

Red Scale (*Aulacaspis rosae*) :

Red Scale insects are reddish brown and use to attack on the old stems and younger shoots. There are found in thousand numbers and form a big colony. They appear and cause more severely damage before and after mansoon season. In small areas of the plant its controlled by rubbing with tooth brush dipped in 0.1% rogor or methylated spirit Malathion 0.1%; Parathion, Metasystox etc. are much effective for scales in larger quantity.

Aphid (*Macrosiphum rosae*):

These are small green colured insects usually appear early in the spring season and used to feed on the tender shoots, buds and flowers of roses. They damage the plants by sucking sap of plant flowers in severed attack and plant parts are malformed flower bled drop off. Aphid can easily be controlled by spraying with Malathion (0.1%), Metasystox (0.2%), Rogor (0.1 to 0.2%) or Metacid etc. Lady bird beetles are natural predators.

Since aphids are attracted to the colour yellow, install sticky yellow traps near your plants. Place yellow containers full of soapy water or water mixed with yellow food colouring at the base of infested plants (Suhardi and Saefullah 2004).

Thrips (*Scivtothrips dorsalis*):

Thrips are very minute, long and Cylinder shaped insects which usually inhabit themseves in the undersurface of tender leaves and suck sap from leaves and flower buds. Deformed flowers are the main signs of attack. Use of neem products, Malathion, rogar and metasystox etc. are effective for controlling the thrips.

Jassids (*Lucerne leaf hopper*) :

It is commonly called as leaf hoppers. These are very small in shape, grey or pale green colored insects. It is causing yellowing or whiting of the attacked surface by sucking the sap and used to give sickly appearance. It can be controlled by spraying with 0.03%, Parathion, 0.1% or 8% thimet as soil applicatons.

Chafer Beetles (*Macroductylus subspinosus*):

The Chafer beetles are usually found and attack on the rose-plants and feed mainly growing point, tender parts and making irregular holes on the leaves. Their intensity is usually found severe during rainy seasons. In soil treatment with 5% aldrin dust or 3% heptachlor dust are effective for controlling the chafer beetles. Use of horticulture oil insecticides effective. This was rose chafer will stick to the leaves and not get washed away by the rain. The organic insecticides pyrethrum (made from chrysanthemum flowers) and rotenone are good effective.

Mealy Bugs (Hemiptera) :

Mealy bugs suck the sap on the bud and flowers of roses. So buds does not open. Spraying of fenitrothion, metasystox, rogor and soil application of phorate and thimet controls the bugs.

Digger Wasps (Hymenoptera):

It attacked on the plants after pruning. They use to dig a hole into the pith of stem through the cut end make a nest there. A fungus entered by the hole and causing die back. Fungus can be controlled by painting the pruning cuts with a fumicidal paints containing 4 parts of each of copper carbonate and red lead along 5 parts of linseed oil. Dry portion of twigs should be removed.

Some Minor Insect-Pests:

There are some other minor insect-pests which Cause damage to rose plants. They are caterpillars rose midge, rose stem girdler, Japanese beetle, mossy rose gall, rose bud warm, saw foles etc. Its effecting different parts of the plant in different growth stages.

Nematodes:

Nematodes are very common plant parasite. There infestation is easily recognized by formation of root galls, malnutrition, decreased shoot growth and leaf chlorosis. These are elongated, more or less cylindrical pests which attack on the roots but can not be seen with naked eye. Nemagon applied through irrigation water at the rate of 10-12 litres per hectare gives satisfactory control and have long residual action but affects the growth of the plants. timic also effectively controls the nematodes but it remains active for a shorter period than nemagon.

(B) Diseases:

(I) Die-Back: It is major disease of rose plants caused by *pp4ia rosarum* fungus. According to disease causes death of the plant from top to downwards. Generally, after pruning twigs become black below the pruned surface, which as time extends in downwardly and killing the whole plant. The stem and roots of the death plants show browning of internal tissues.

The easiest method of control measure is to cut away the affected parts and burn it. The secateur should be disinfected with spirit and cut ends immediately coated with a paste containing 4 parts of copper carbonate, 4 part of red lead and 5 parts of linseed oil. The diseased twigs should always be pruned up to 5-5 cm below and oblique with the visible blackened portion of the tissue. Fungicides moncozets, funginex etc.

Red Spider Mite (*Panonychus ulmi*, *Tetranychus sp.*):

These are very tiny, polyphagous, red to brown coloured pests found in large number on the underside of leaves covered with fine silky webs. Its protonymphal stage causes the maximum damage. Affected leaves look very dusty, turn yellow and fall. Infestation is usually found in the warm and dry seasons. Spray of Sulphur, Keithane, Marestan, dicofol etc. helps to control the mite.

Powdery Mildew (*Podosphaera pannosa*) :

Powdery Mildew caused by fungus *Sphaerotheca Pannosa*. It appears due to day warm and nights are cool. All the aerial parts of plant are generally affected and one finds white powdery growth of the fungus particularly on lower side of the leaves. Flower buds are usually affected and fail to open and are found to be damaged. Fungicides benlate, bavistin, nimrod, saprol, calixin etc. are very useful in controlling this disease. Sulphur dust needs to be applied at about 10 days intervals.

Rust (*Phragmidium* spp.) :

It is common to be found in warm and humid areas and caused by fungus *phragmidium* species. In infested plants leaflets and petioles showed reddish orange pustules. The colour of pustules changes to black after sometimes. It gives effect on the flower production. Application of folpet, Phalton, Maneb, mixture of sulphur controls the disease. Spraying of Zineb (2000 ppm) at fortnightly interval has also been recommended to control the rust. Remove and destroy all infected leaves. A baking soda solution may also be used.

Back Spot (*Diplocarpon rosae*):

The disease is characterized by dark brown, circular spots with fringe borders, present on both side of leaflets. At the later stage leaf become yellow in colour and ultimately fall. Leaf buds are not developed and the flower buds are also affected. The infected leaves should be clipped off, taken out of field and burnt.

Stem blight (*Diplocarpon rosae*) :

It is blight disease caused by fungus and associated with die-back, several tan-coloured spots appear on the stems, particularly in older plants which merge together and usually spread to the whole bark. Regular sprays of captan at 2000 ppm and such other fungicides control the infection.

Alternaria leaf spot (*Alternaria*):

It is important one and causes heavy loss during the rainy season. Spraying at weekly intervals with captan or Zineb at 2000 ppm has been recommended for its control.

Root rot (*Trichoderma viridae*):

It is caused by *Trichoderma viride*. The root gets decayed. Later the leaves turn yellow and the plant dies. Exposer of roots, incorporation of dry wood ash and use of bavistin are the suggested measures.

Rose-Wilt (Verticillium):

It is caused by Virus. Leaflets recurring at the tip of young shoots. Defoliation may happen, with leaves turning yellow and falling off, The stem also gets infected severely and ultimately whole plant dies. Control of aphids is necessary because it transmit the disease and helps to control the infection. The affected plants should be removed and burnt and all possible precautions should be observed.

Rose Mosaic Virus:

It is also found mostly on green house roses. Chlorofil areas alongwith midrib of leaflets localied distortion are the main symptom of this disease. Infected plants should be destroyed and never used for propagation.

Other diseases:

There are several other diseases like black mosaic, botrytis blight, leaf-spots and downey mildew are the fungal disease; bactori leaf spot and crown gall among bacterial disease and Rose streak virus, strawberry latent ring- spot virus; rose leaf curl, rose spring dwarf among also effecting the viral rose cultivation and flower production (Hoffers *et al.* 2014).

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